

ELECTRON AND THERMAL TRANSPORT MECHANISM IN CNT-NETWORK COMPOSITES FOR STRAIN RESILIENT ELECTRONICS

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ABSTRACT

Electronic devices to perform and survive in high impact scenarios undergo high strain-rate environments are usually exposed to highly dynamic impact, extreme temperature and moisture fluctuations. To introduce strain resiliency, in this work we use carbon nanotube (CNT) mesh (network) to provide high strain resiliency. However, the CNT junction materials composition is known to be controlling materials design parameter because the CNT junctions undergo extreme strain gradient during impact scenario critically affecting the both electronic and thermal properties. Non Equilibrium Green Function (NEGF) with Tight Binding Molecular Dynamics (TBMD) is employed to analyze the electron transmission through the CNT contacts. The incorporation of the TBMD through appropriate parameterization allows us to accommodate a significant large number of molecules to appropriately represent to CNT contact morphology for different CNT contact configuration, chirality, and deformation. Similarly for thermal transport across the CNT junctions, the traditional Non Equilibrium Molecular Dynamics (NEMD) is used to study the effect of CNT deformation, CNT chirality, and aspect ratio on the contact thermal contact resistance. It is observed that the interface thermal conductance (inverse of resistance) increases with CNT aspect ratio, but the rate of conductance decreases with increased aspect ratio, which is due to the fact that at higher aspect ratio the transverse phonon modes (primary contributor to interface transport) become weaker as compared to that of the longitudinal modes. In the case of electronic transport across the CNT contact, there is several mechanisms influence the phenomena. The CNT contact modification with polymeric functionalization (presence of any polymer molecule) significantly degrades the electronic transmission coefficient and hence the conductance. The smaller diameter CNTs are preferred for improved electronic contact conductance because of increased overlapping electron orbitals between the CNT surfaces at the contact.

1 INTRODUCTION

The electronics device design and production is dominated by the commercial sector [1] due to its market size as compared to military specific applications. The electronic devices in defense (military) systems are to perform for longer period (~ 10x life as compared to commercial electronics) and in demanding harsh environment (high strain, cyclic temperature, moisture, etc.). Because of prohibitive developmental cost associated with application-specific integrated circuits (ASICs), especially in low volume consumption in defense industry, the ASICs are almost entirely fabricated from commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components. The current COTS-based circuit design in defense electronics,

however, limits the functionality and performance. The observed failure modes in COTS circuits in high g impact (high strain rate) tests predominantly found to be interconnects failure (breakage and delamination from circuit board) and chip-substrate interface delamination [2]. From the observed failure modes, it is inferred that implementing ductile (high-strain to failure) interconnects materials to replace brittle solder would make immediate impact to strain-resiliency to integrated circuits in electronic devices.

The objective of this work is to develop a highly compliant (stretchable and high strain to failure) interconnect materials, as solder replacement, with a goal of achieving the electrical property characteristics of that of solder. To propose a nanocomposite, interconnected CNT mesh embedded in highly ductile (high strain to failure) polymer, as compliant interconnect materials, Figure 1. The hypothesis behind this approach is that the CNT mesh interconnectivity in the polymer phase (matrix) will provide the desired electrical conductivity even in the high-strain deformation states. The major challenge in this concept work is in the CNT contact (network connectivity) design to ensure desired electrical and thermal (local heating at the contact due to contact thermal resistance) properties even under high strain. Further, careful measurement CNT contact resistance [3, 4], both thermal and electrical, indicate that the contact resistance is several order of magnitude ($\sim 10^6$) higher than that of CNTs itself. Thus, proper design of CNT junction morphology is exceedingly important for the design of this CNT network. In this paper, we present materials modeling to study electron and thermal transport characteristics at the CNT contacts and assess CNT contact design approaches. As a first step of the CNT contact analysis, the Van der Waals contacts are studied.

Figure 1. Proposed CNT mesh for strain-resilient electronic materials.

The modeling of the electron transport across a CNT junction was performed using Non Equilibrium Green Function (NEGF) to study the effect of CNT chirality, atomic orientation/alignment, etc. Then, the probability value of the junction electronic transfer function was used in the effective medium theory to obtain the CNT network electrical conductivity [14]. For the thermal conductance across the CNT contact was studied using widely used non equilibrium molecular dynamics. The computational approach and predicted data are discussed below.

2 ELECTRON TRANSPORT (ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY)

We used a non-equilibrium Green's function analysis based on density functional tight binding Hamiltonian (DFTB-NEGF) [5] to calculate the electron transmission function in the contact between two identical single wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) with (5,5), (6,6), (8,8), (10,10) or (15,15) chirality under Bohr-Oppenheimer approximation of static ion configuration. Considering polymer being insulative to electron transport, we assume that electron tunneling between two CNTs at the junctions and no participation of polymer phase in the electron transport phenomena at the junction. Previous calculations have shown that for a polymer filled gap of 2 Å gap size increase in accommodating the polymer in the gap, the tunneling resistance increases by approximately 2 orders of magnitude [6]. Therefore, we assume that only direct contacts between nanotubes make an appreciable contribution to the electrical conductivity of the composites. This assumption is to some

extent supported by multiple experimental studies of fiber composites that show conductivity following well a power law dependence on fiber volume fraction near the percolation threshold [7] as predicted by classical percolation theory.

In this study, several molecular configurations of the contact are analyzed by varying a gap size between two pristine nanotubes and nanotubes' atomic alignment at the junctions. It is also assumed that thermal fluctuations of the nanotube shape do not disturb the charge density largely enough to affect the electron transmission function of the gap. Furthermore, the temperature in Fermi-Dirac distribution can be set to 0 K because our modeling show that it does not much change the electron transmission function near room temperature. Therefore, our emphasis is on studying the effect of temperature on the fluctuations of a gap size between two nanotubes, which in turn dictates the fluctuations of the electrical conductivity of CNT network.

Figure 2. Molecular models that were used to calculate electron transport in the gap between two metallic nanotubes: (a) two “infinite” (6,6) SWCNTs crossing at 90° angle with scattering region (green), electron source (red) and electron drain (blue) (a); top view of the scattering region showing two CNTs in atom-to-atom, atom-to-ring, and ring-to-ring orientation, (b-d, respectively); side view of the of the scattering region showing two circular CNTs (e) and two deformed CNTs with the same separation distance in three mutual orientations (f-h).

The representative snapshots of molecular models are shown in Figure 2. Calculations were performed using DFTB+NEGF code [8] that employs NEGF formalism for calculating steady-state electrical current through the molecular structure with applied external voltage. The constant bias voltage is applied across the source and drain electrodes. For configuration shown in Figure 2a, the device, or the central electron scattering part of the model (marked green), consists of 624 atoms in two crossing (6, 6) CNTs that are in contact with four electrodes (marked red for source and blue for drain). Each electrode consists of 96 carbon atoms arranged in perfect (6, 6) CNT structure infinitely extended through semi-infinite boundary conditions in horizontal direction. Because of these extended electrodes, this model represents a system of two infinitely long crossing nanotubes, with a single isolated contact. With two crossing SWCNT setup, we studied the effect of mutual tube orientation by rotating each tube along its axis to ensure three possible configurations: i) the two closest atoms of two tubes are facing directly each other (atom-to-atom, or A2A orientation in Fig. 2b); ii) the closest atom of a tube is facing the center of the ring on the opposite tube (atom-to-ring, or A2R orientation in Fig. 2c); and iii) two closest rings on two tubes are aligned on top of each other (ring-to-ring, or R2R orientation in Fig. 2d). The separation distance between two nanotube surfaces is varied between 2.35 Å and 3.15 Å, and nanotube chirality varied between (6, 6) and (12, 12) to study the effect of diameter on electron transport. The value of crossing angle between nanotubes was restricted to 90° as required

by DFTB+NEGF Poisson solver implemented on quasi-periodic grid in Cartesian coordinates. However, our modeling has shown that the effective gap conductance exhibits weak dependence on geometrical parameters (other than separation distance). Therefore, we do not expect the dependence on the crossing angle to be stronger than that of the effective crossing area, and probably even weaker as was shown for the parallel contact [9]. Considering this, we believe that the results for 90° crossing angle represent a general case of network with distribution of crossing angles, and is quite appropriate for analyzing the physics of electrical transport through such network.

Figure 3. (a) I-V characteristics calculated for two crossing (6, 6) CNTs separated by distance of 2.75 Å (up triangles) and 2.95 Å (down triangles), and for equilibrium structure with polymer chain inserted in the gap (squares). Lines represent linear fits with effective resistance shown in the legend. (b) Effective contact resistance between two metallic CNTs separated by 2.35 Å in three different orientations as shown in Fig.1 (b-d), plotted as a function of tube diameter; (c) electron density isosurface plots with the same iso value of 10^{-6} , plotted for (6,6) and (12,12) nanotube contacts with same separation distance 2.35 Å.

The effect of organic molecule or polymer chain, placed in the gap between two nanotubes, on the contact electrical conductance was studied first. The structure was created as shown in Fig. 2(a), with an addition of single polyethylene (PE) chain into the gap followed my energy minimization run that brings the tubes to a new equilibrium separation distance (7.27Å between CNTs). The conductance calculated for this structure was compared with the conductance between the same tubes without the PE chain, located at equilibrium separation distance of 2.95 Å and at smaller distance of 2.75 Å. The resulting $I(V)$ curves are presented in Fig. 3(a) in a semi-log scale. This simulation shows that the insertion of the polymer chain into the gap between two nanotubes essentially disrupts the electrical contact, making the electrical current smaller by 4 orders of magnitude. We therefore assume that at least for CNT-polymer composites with nonpolar and nonconductive matrix, the contribution of the CNT-CNT contacts mediated by matrix molecules is very negligible and thus the direct CNT-CNT contacts is not analyzed in details further.

When the separation distance between nanotubes is fixed, the gap resistance increases with tube diameter and also depends on tube rotational orientation. Now, to study the effects tube rotational orientation and tube chirality, the effective resistance is plotted in Fig. 3(b) in semi-log scale against tube diameter for three studied tube rotational orientations explained in Fig.2 (b-d). With increasing nanotube diameter, the effective distance between the atoms between the adjacent nanotubes increases resulting in increased interface contact resistance, Fig 3(b). Further, it is inferred that the ring-to-ring (R2R) atomic alignment provided higher cumulative electronic interactions yielding lower resistance (higher conductance), Fig 3(b). Additionally, as shown if Fig 3(c), because of electron orbitals being pushed outwards as CNT diameter goes down, more electron orbital overlap is observed in smaller diameter CNTs and thus yields lower resistance, Fig 3(c).

Effective Medium Analysis of Electrical Conductivity in CNT Network

It was shown in the previous section that electron tunneling transport in CNT-CNT cross contact can be characterized by a single effective resistance parameter that have a typical value of several M-Ohms. If we neglect the electrical resistance of the nanotubes and consider only contacts, the percolated system can be modeled as a classical resistor network shown in Fig 4(b). Each nanotube is considered as a node, and the network coordination number, z , (appeared in Fig 4(c) is equal to the average number of contacts per nanotube that is around 2.6 (i.e., $\ln(z/2-1) = -1.9$, shown in Fig 4(c)) at percolation. In Fig 4(c) below, the comparison of sparse (2.6 contacts per CNT; $\ln(z/2-1) = -1.9$) and dense (40,000 contacts per CNT; $\ln(z/2-1) = 10$) network with experimental data indicates that a sparse network of a few contacts (2 or 3) per CNT is adequate to achieving the desired conductivity.

Figure 4. (a) Percolated network of conducting fibers, (b) the equivalent resistor network built in the assumption that all electrical resistance of fiber network is placed at the contacts. (c) Comparison of predicted CNT network epoxy composite conductivity with measured data (CNT-epoxy composite with 2% loading [11], in MWCNT mat [10]). Solid and dashed lines show fit results if dense and sparse network limits.

3 THERMAL TRANSPORT (CONDUCTIVITY)

Thermal energy transfer at single-wall carbon nanotube (SWCNT) interconnects is studied using non-equilibrium molecular dynamics simulation; the computational approach is discussed in [12, 13]. The role of various geometrical and structural (length, diameter, chirality) as well as external (deformation and strain) carbon nanotube (CNT) parameters have been explored for the first time to estimate total as well as area-normalized thermal conductance across an X-shaped interface interconnects, Figure 5. It is shown that CNT aspect ratio and degree of the lateral as well as tensile deformation play a significant role in determining extent of thermal energy exchange across CNT contacts, while CNT chirality has a negligible influence on interface thermal transport. Depending on the CNT diameter, aspect ratio, and degree of deformation at contact interface, thermal conductance values can vary significantly – by an order of magnitude for total conductance and a factor of 3 to 4 for area-normalized conductance.

Figure 5: Schematic of a representative physically interacting SWCNT pair in an X-shaped geometry (perspective view: main figure; top view: top-right corner) as considered in this study for calculation of thermal conductance. L represents the length of the SWCNT. Color scheme: fixed carbon atoms (black); hot thermostated carbon atoms (red); cold thermostated carbon atoms (blue); unthermostated carbon atoms (cyan). The specifics of studied SWCNTs' chirality are also shown in as in top-left corner. The overall geometry of the system in a large slab is shown at the bottom; red and blue colors are shown to differentiate the CNTs.

Figure 6. Log-log plots of SWCNTs interface thermal conductance ($\text{MW/m}^2\text{-K}$) as a function of geometry aspect ratio ($\eta_2=L/D$) for different diameter CNTs. Data color scheme for different diameter SWCNTs is shown in legends. In (a), a power-law scaling of $1/3$ is shown as a guide for the eye.

The observed master-curves, shown in Figure 6, revealed that higher aspect ratio (i.e., fewer contacts per unit CNT length) offer higher conductivity. However, the rate of increase in conductivity decreases with increasing aspect ratio. There are many factors attribute to this phenomenon. As the aspect ratio increases, longitudinal phonon modes become more dominant than the transverse modes. Since, transverse modes are the primary contributors of interface thermal conductance at the contact, thus the rate of increase in conductance decreases with increasing aspect ratio. Another contributing

factor is that as the aspect ratio increases, the CNTs become more compliant, deform easily, and do not conform to the adjacent CNT surface as in with shorter aspect ratio – thus causing reduction in the transverse thermal conductivity.

4 CONCLUSIONS

To introduce strain resiliency in the electronic materials we propose to use carbon nanotube (CNT) mesh (network) to provide high strain resiliency. The CNT junction materials composition is known to be controlling materials design parameter because junctions undergo extreme strain gradient during impact scenario critically affecting the both electronic and thermal properties. It is observed that the interface thermal conductance (inverse of resistance) increases with CNT aspect ratio, but the rate of conductance decreases with increased aspect ratio, which is due to the fact that at higher aspect ratio the transverse phonon modes (primary contributor to interface transport) become weaker as compared to that of the longitudinal modes. In the case of electronic transport across the CNT contact, there is several mechanisms influence the phenomena. The CNT contact modification with polymeric functionalization (presence of any polymer molecule) significantly degrades the electronic transmission coefficient and hence the conductance. The smaller diameter CNTs are preferred for improved electronic contact conductance because of increased overlapping electron orbitals between the CNT surfaces at the contact.

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